

SoftHand Pro Haptic Framework

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Abstract. The proposed study plan introduces the SoftHand Pro (SHP) Haptic Framework to enhance the sensory experience and functionality of the SHP, an underactuated soft prosthetic hand. Central to this framework are three distinct wearable and embedded feedback devices: the Wearable Integrated Soft Haptic (WISH) device, conveying grasping force information to the user; the Vibro-Inertial Bionic Enhancement System (VIBES), providing surface information; and the Prosthetic Upper Limb Sensory Enhancement Device, offering dual sensory feedback. The framework aims to empower individuals to select customized haptic feedback options. In this proposed study plan, the SHP haptic framework is detailed, leveraging consolidated findings from usability tests and subjective questionnaires of each device. Furthermore, broader implications for prosthetic users are explored. Ongoing research aims to validate the user-centred haptic feedback framework in real-life scenarios with a larger sample size.

Keywords: Haptics · Prosthetic · Vibrotactile Feedback · Force Feedback

1 Introduction

Creating non-invasive upper-limb haptic devices aims to restore tactile and kinesthetic cues to prosthetic users. While mechano-tactile, electrotactile, and vibrotactile stimulation are prominent approaches for transmitting tactile information, current solutions primarily focus on single-type feedback, limiting choices and adaptability [5]. Moreover, few commercially available sensorized bionic prostheses (e.g. the Vincent Hand [1]) offer only single-modal haptic solutions.

In our prior study [3] on user feedback preferences (e.g., vibration, multimodal stimuli), participants subjectively chose preferred feedback, leading to very subject- and task-dependent choices, and suggested an overall integration of the devices. Thus, in this paper, we introduce the SoftHand Pro (SHP) [6] haptic framework (Fig.1), comprising three distinct embedded tactile feedback devices for SHP prosthetic users. The framework includes the Wearable Integrated Soft Haptic (WISH) device [2], a force feedback device transmitting grasping force information to the subject; the Vibro-Inertial Bionic Enhancement System (VIBES) [7], a vibrotactile device which provides surface information to the user and the Prosthetic Upper Limb Sensory Enhancement (PULSE) device [8], offering both force and vibrotactile feedback. The framework prioritizes a user-centred approach, empowering SHP users to select their preferred feedback type based on their needs. In this short paper, we outline the features of the framework based on the results obtained from the individual devices.

Fig. 1. Overview of the different haptic feedback options with the SoftHand Pro prosthetic device: 1) Vibrotactile feedback (VIBES); 2) Force Feedback (WISH); 3) Vibrotactile and Force Feedback.

2 The SHP Haptic Framework

The SHP haptic framework integrates three fully wearable and embedded devices: the VIBES, the WISH, and the PULSE (Fig. 1). The VIBES utilizes two coin-type exciters to transmit surface information (e.g. texture and first-contact cues). Each exciter comprises a coil enclosing a neodymium magnet, while the system integrates two Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs, MPU-9250) positioned on two phalanges of the SHP. The VIBES control strategy processes acceleration signals from IMUs and then maps them into PWM values for activating vibrotactile actuators through electronic boards[4]. The WISH device features a pneumatic system for force feedback, consisting of two silicone chambers connected to a mechanical actuation unit via a silicone pipe. The chambers are made from biocompatible silicone (Ecoflex 30), ensuring safe skin contact. The WISH pressure stimulation maps SHP hand data to the feedback interface, associating hand current values with a corresponding pressure value. The PULSE features the WISH and the VIBES devices, merges control strategies from its components, and includes a switch for users to activate or deactivate feedback systems. Please refer to [7, 2, 8].

Rather than being characterized by fixed features, this framework underscores the importance of adaptability and flexibility within the prosthetic device. It provides SHP users with the autonomy to select their preferred feedback type from the current selection of three tactile feedback options totally embedded in the prosthesis. For instance, if they find both types of feedback beneficial in certain life situations, they can opt for the PULSE. Users can adjust the positioning and number of actuators on the severity and nature of their limb loss, thereby facilitating the customization of the device to suit their needs. In cases where the subject has undergone target muscle reinnervation, the position of the actuators can be adjusted to be in contact with the skin of the residual limb more sensitive to those sensations. Additionally, users are free to deactivate the feedback at their discretion rather than keep it continuously active.

About the preliminary tests, each device underwent physical and psychophysical characterizations, followed by usability tests designed for specific feedback types with able-bodied subjects and pilot experiments with a prosthetic user. The VIBES functionality was tested in Passive and Active Texture Identification of different sandpapers [7]. The WISH device was evaluated in cylinder-softness discrimination and fragile object manipulation tasks [2]. The PULSE device was assessed to determine if concurrent stimuli would distract users in a haptic discrimination task involving the recognition of compliance and textures of objects [8]. User evaluations were conducted using subjective questionnaires and the System Usability Scale [9].

3 Preliminary Results

Results of texture discrimination with VIBES were favourable, with consistent behaviours among able-bodied subjects during passive exploration, yielding a Just Noticeable Difference (JND) of $87.30 \mu\text{m}$. Active texture identification also showed improvement, with a prosthetic user achieving a recognition accuracy of 52% compared to 40% without the feedback. In the WISH cylinder-softness discrimination task, significantly higher accuracy was observed with the device, reaching 100% with feedback and 75% without. With the PULSE device, both able-bodied participants and prosthetic users significantly improved recognition of object texture and compliance compared to conditions without it, achieving discrimination accuracies of 85.4% and 83.3%, respectively, with the PULSE device and 60.4% and 62.5% without. The VIBES System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire scored positively at 77.5, indicating system intuitiveness. WISH received a total SUS score of 70. However, PULSE scored lower at 55, though, from the questionnaires, neither device caused discomfort or confusion to the subjects.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

In summary, we introduced the SoftHand Pro Haptic framework, which provides personalized haptic feedback through three embedded devices. Our initial findings suggest positive outcomes regarding task-specific performance and user perception. However, the usability of concurrent stimuli resulted in a lower SUS score, indicating the need for further refinement. With various feedback options available to users, this framework shows potential for improving the long-term usability of prosthetics. Nonetheless, additional testing is necessary. Our future research will assess the overall performance of the framework with a larger sample size. Additionally, we will explore additional types of haptic feedback and investigate user preferences regarding actuator positioning.

5 Disclosure of Interests

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References

1. The vincent hand, <https://www.vincentssystem.de/en/vincent-evolution4>
2. Barontini, F., et al.: Wearable integrated soft haptics in a prosthetic socket. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* (2021)
3. Barontini, F., et al.: Tactile feedback in upper limb prosthetics: A pilot study on trans-radial amputees comparing different haptic modalities. *IEEE Transactions on Haptics* **16**, 760–769 (2023), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:263742226>
4. Della Santina, C., et al.: The quest for natural machine motion: An open platform to fast-prototyping articulated soft robots. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine* (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MRA.2016.2636366>
5. Dey, A., et al.: A decade of haptic feedback for upper limb prostheses. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics* (2023)
6. Godfrey, S.B., et al.: The softand pro: Functional evaluation of a novel, flexible, and robust myoelectric prosthesis. *PloS one* (2018)
7. Ivani, A.S., et al.: Vibes: Vibro-inertial bionic enhancement system in a prosthetic socket. In: *ICORR* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICORR58425.2023.10304768>
8. Ivani, A.S., et al.: Prosthetic upper-limb sensory enhancement (pulse): a dual haptic feedback device in a prosthetic socket. In: *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)* (2024), accepted
9. Lewis, J.R.: The system usability scale: Past, present, and future. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction* (2018)